

User feedback logbook (D5.1)

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Document history

Changes		
v1.0	2025-05-19	● Initial version

Introduction

The following is the result of a user survey conducted in May 2025 among users who had requested an EU Project Community on Zenodo. In total 674 users were invited to participate and 78 responded (12% response rate).

The description for D5.1 User feedback logbook is:

Report collecting all user feedback for all features. This document will be updated regularly to meet the needs of the project development process.

It was agreed with DG RTD in the project coordination board to conduct a user survey to collect end-user feedback from real-world usage rather than having feedback only on draft designs. This report presents the results of the survey.

The survey was designed to collect primarily free-form feedback in order to gather more detailed feedback from. The survey was conducted on the EUSurvey platform, the survey was fully anonymous and participation was voluntary. Participants were informed that the results would be analysed and reported publicly in a summarized form without individually identifying characteristics and that individual answers would not be shared publicly. See the “Survey” section to view the full survey as presented to users.

Summary

- Overall respondents expressed appreciation for the service.
- Respondents represented a good mix both in terms of how often they used Zenodo, and in terms of how long they had used Zenodo.
- Respondents use EU Project Communities for dissemination, visibility and Horizon Europe compliance/FAIR.
- New users learn about EU Open Research Repository from peers, project officers while existing users learn about it from Zenodo and peers (this was the main difference between new and existing users that was discovered in the survey).
- Other repositories: The projects also use primarily software repositories (GitHub/GitLab), institutional/domain-specific repositories and project websites.
- Features:
 - New and existing users largely agreed on which features were most useful and which were most difficult.
 - *Easy upload and data sharing*: There's general agreement between new/existing users that easy data sharing, in particular ease of getting a DOI and integration with EU project databases, is the most useful feature/capability.
 - *Authors and metadata autofilling*: The most difficult is to add authors and that in general the form is long and time-consuming to fill, and that they would like more automated filling of the form.
 - *Search/discovery/usability*: Some users expressed difficulties in searching and overall complexity of the interface.

- *Communities*: There's general appreciation of many community features (member management, reviews etc) and as well as good suggestions for improvements of these features.

Results

How often do you use your EU Project Community on Zenodo?

		Answers	Ratio
Never		2	2.56 %
Rarely		15	19.23 %
Sometimes		41	52.56 %
Often		20	25.64 %
No Answer		0	0.00 %

Were you already using Zenodo prior to creating your EU Project Community?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes, three months or less		6	7.69 %
Yes, one year or less		10	12.82 %
Yes, more than a year		12	15.38 %
Yes, more than three years		20	25.64 %
No		30	38.46 %
No Answer		0	0.00 %

What types of research outputs do you primarily share in your EU Project Community?

		Answers	Ratio
Peer-reviewed scientific publications		44	56.41 %
Data		48	61.54 %
Software		20	25.64 %
Project deliverables/reports		43	55.13 %
Presentations and posters		36	46.15 %
Other		6	7.69 %
No Answer		2	2.56 %

How did you hear about the option to create an EU Project Community as part of the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo?

1. Zenodo website (20 mentions)

Users discovered the feature while using Zenodo directly:

- Saw banners or homepage messages.
- Found it during submission or while browsing communities.
- Encountered the option in the user interface or help sections.

2. Colleagues/peers (18 mentions)

Many users learned about the feature from peers:

- Recommendations from colleagues, supervisors, or students.
- Shared experience within other research groups or collaborations.

3. Project Officer / coordinator / partner (14 mentions)

The information was shared through formal project structures:

- Project officers or coordinators introduced the feature.
- Guidance came from partners handling dissemination or data management.

4. Previous project experience (4 mentions)

Some respondents knew about the feature due to:

- Experience managing previous EU-funded projects.
- Familiarity with Zenodo from earlier programmes like FP7 or H2020.

What was your main motivation for requesting and using an EU Project Community?

1. Dissemination and visibility (18 mentions)

Users were motivated by the desire to:

- Increase the visibility of their project outputs.
- Consolidate and showcase results in a public and recognisable space.

- Reach broader audiences, including peers, stakeholders, and the general public.

2. Compliance with open access / FAIR Requirements (16 mentions)

Many respondents used the EU Project Community to:

- Fulfil Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe open access mandates.
- Ensure data was FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).
- Meet obligations set by funding agencies or institutional policies.

3. Trusted/open repository (5 mentions)

Users appreciated that Zenodo offers:

- A reliable and long-term preservation solution.
- An open, recognised, and transparent publishing environment.
- A safe place for outputs post-project.

4. Data sharing and openness (5 mentions)

Respondents highlighted goals such as:

- Facilitating reuse and openness of datasets and code.
- Making outputs accessible to the research community and public.
- Promoting collaborative and open science.

5. Centralised and official record keeping (5 mentions)

Some wanted:

- A single, approved location for curating all project materials.
- An official, structured way to organise, manage, and present outputs.
- Assurance that outputs remain accessible after project completion.

What other repositories (if any) do you use for your EU project? And if so, for what type/s of material?

1. Software repositories (GitHub, GitLab) (12 mentions)

Primarily used for:

- Source code
- Data scripts
- Experiment tracking
- These platforms support collaborative software development and version control.

2. None / Only Zenodo (10 mentions)

- These respondents exclusively use Zenodo or reported no use of any other repository.

3. Institutional / Domain-specific repositories (9 mentions)

Used for:

- Peer-reviewed publications and datasets
- Discipline-specific databases (e.g., HAL, SEANOE, e-ciencia, Biblio, Argos, arXiv, NCBI, PhilPapers)
- These repositories are often hosted by universities or research institutions.

4. Institutional / internal repositories (6 mentions)

Used internally by organisations (e.g. SharePoint, Google Drive) for:

- Private documents
- Project management resources

5. Project website (5 mentions)

Used to share:

- Newsletters
- Deliverables
- General project outputs and dissemination materials

What feature/capability was the easiest or most useful for you?

1. Uploading Data or Code (10 mentions)

Users appreciated the simplicity and efficiency of uploading files, datasets, or code to Zenodo:

- Uploading materials was consistently reported as straightforward.
- The interface for uploading documents and code was seen as intuitive.
- Users could complete uploads with minimal effort or technical complexity.

2. DOIs (9 mentions)

The automatic or quick assignment of DOIs was one of the most praised features:

- Users found DOI assignment easy and fast.
- DOI reservation and versioning were perceived as reliable and useful.
- Features allowing DOI creation for unpublished or external materials were seen as particularly beneficial.

3. EU project integration (8 mentions)

Zenodo's integration with EU project infrastructure was frequently noted as useful:

- Automatic recognition of project acronyms.
- Ease of linking outputs to funding sources and the EC portal.
- Seamless connection to the EU Open Research Repository was valued by multiple respondents.

4. Community management (5 mentions)

Users found community setup and management effective:

- Creating a community and adding records was simple.
- Reviewing submissions and managing membership within a community was praised.
- Linking deposited content to communities was clear and worked reliably.

5. General satisfaction (3 mentions)

Some users expressed that all features were useful or had no specific preference and indicated overall satisfaction with Zenodo's capabilities.

What feature/capability was the most difficult or least useful for you?

1. Author and contributor management (7 mentions)

Users faced multiple challenges with how Zenodo handles author information:

- IDs (e.g., ORCID) did not reliably match authors to their profiles.
- Author names are not retained between uploads, even within the same community.
- Contributors must be manually added one by one, which becomes tedious for large teams.
- It's not possible to edit author ORCID linkages if another user submitted the record with your ORCID on it.
- The interface for entering authors is seen as time-consuming and lacks automation (e.g., pulling metadata from a DOI).
- General frustration with the effort required to input or retrieve consistent contributor data.

2. Metadata entry and upload interface complexity (6 mentions)

Several users struggled with the effort and complexity required to input data and metadata:

- Completing all metadata fields is time-consuming.
- The upload form has too many options, overwhelming new users.
- Users expressed a desire for a more streamlined upload process, especially for communities.
- Manual adjustments were required when publishing via GitHub.
- Lack of flexibility to correct or adjust metadata after a submission is approved.
- The interface is not intuitive; users need time to become comfortable.

3. Search, discovery, and navigation Issues (4 mentions)

Users had difficulty finding specific content or navigating the system:

- Searching within communities or for persons was unreliable.
- It was unclear whether PDF contents were indexed or how best to search for requests.
- Discovering one's own communities or similar projects was not intuitive.
- Lack of guidance on effective keyword usage in search.
- Download of analytics reports

4. DOI and versioning issues (3 mentions)

Challenges related to DOI assignment and handling of versions:

- Problems with duplicated DOI numbers.
- Confusion or dissatisfaction with how versioning works for deposited objects.
- Frustration that DOI metadata (like authors) isn't automatically retrieved.

5. Community management (4 mentions)

Users reported unclear or cumbersome processes related to community usage:

- Difficult with approving a previously rejected submission.
- Difficulty in setting up or introducing a community to project members.
- Lack of clarity around tagging submissions to a community, especially when curators have limited editing rights.
- Confusion in how to establish a community, requiring external help from university services.

6. Integration with external systems (3 mentions)

Users struggled with systems that Zenodo attempts to connect with:

- Difficulties integrating with the CORDIS system.
- Problems with seamless importing into the participant portal.
- Lack of clear status or feedback from external services like ROR when setting up institutional profiles (i.e. getting a ROR id).

7. General usability and onboarding (2 mentions)

Broader usability concerns, especially for newcomers:

- The site isn't intuitive and has a steep learning curve.
- Beginners may find the platform overwhelming without support or documentation.

What features or capabilities would you like to see added?

1. Metadata autofill and memory (5 mentions)

Users want Zenodo to make metadata entry more efficient:

- Automatically fill metadata fields (e.g., using DOIs, uploaded files, or ORCID).
- Import/export features from e.g. BibTeX
- Remember previous authors or collaborators.
- Pre-fill forms based on past submissions or linked projects.
- More vocabularies instead of only GEMET, EuroSciVoc and MeSH.

2. Repository linking / interoperability (4 mentions)

Requests for broader integrations with other platforms:

- Connect with CORDIS, EMODnet, Scopus, IPCHEM, JRC.
- Enable cross-references to other repositories.
- Improve compatibility with external aggregators.

4. Community management (3 mentions)

Suggestions to improve community workflows:

- Improved review/approval workflows
- Add records to a community without user resubmission.
- Enable admin control over submissions.
- Allow linking between communities.

5. Granular access control (3 mentions)

Users want finer control over access rights:

- Assign different permissions to different collaborators.
- Control access to individual files within a deposit (e.g., anonymized vs. restricted datasets).
- Maintain user control instead of giving full access to repository maintainers.

Do you have any other feedback regarding the EU Open Research Repository or Zenodo that you'd like to share?

1. No feedback / positive only (13 mentions)

The majority of respondents had no additional suggestions or only positive remarks:

- Expressed appreciation for the platform and its role in the research community.
- Common responses included “Thanks”, “Great service”, or simply “No”.

2. Training and Documentation (2 mentions)

Users expressed a desire for:

- Webinars, guides, or videos to better understand and utilise the platform.
- More information on advanced or community features.

3. Privacy concern (1 mention)

A user expressed concern related to the difficulty in managing rights for videos where participants may revoke consent, conflicting with Zenodo's permanence.

4. Metadata automation / FAIR reminders (1 mention)

Suggestions to improve efficiency and data quality:

- Auto-populate metadata from grant agreements.
- Provide reminders or checks for open access and FAIR compliance.

5. Confusion about EU Ecosystem Integration (1 mention)

One user found the broader ecosystem (OpenAIRE, ARGOS, CORDIS) confusing compared to standalone Zenodo use.

Survey

Demographics

* How often do you use your EU Project Community on Zenodo?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often

This field is required.

* Were you already using Zenodo prior to creating your EU Project Community?

- Yes, three months or less
- Yes, one year or less
- Yes, more than a year
- Yes, more than three years
- No

This field is required.

How did you hear about the option to create an EU Project Community as part of the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo?

Your usage of the EU Project Community

What was your main motivation for requesting and using an EU Project Community?

What types of research outputs do you primarily share in your EU Project Community?

- Peer-reviewed scientific publications
- Data
- Software
- Project deliverables/reports
- Presentations and posters
- Other

What other repositories (if any) do you use for your EU project? And if so, for what type/s of material?

Features

What feature/capability was **the easiest or most useful** for you?

What feature/capability was the **most difficult or least useful** for you?

Future: What features or capabilities would you like to see added?

Other feedback

Do you have any other feedback regarding the EU Open Research Repository or Zenodo that you'd like to share?